

SIMULATION OF TEMPERATURE AND CURING PROFILES IN PULTRUDED COMPOSITE RODS

Basuki R Suratno, Lin Ye and Yiu-Wing Mai

Centre for Advanced Materials Technology (CAMT), Department of Mechanical and Mechatronic Engineering, The University of Sydney, NSW 2006, Australia

SUMMARY: Pultrusion is one of many composite manufacturing techniques with potential for rapid and cost-effective production. In this paper, an iterative procedure was developed to simulate the pultrusion process of polymer matrix composites, involving both heat transfer and curing sub-models. A two-dimensional finite element model was applied to simulate heat transfer and temperature profiles inside the die during the pultrusion process, which was coupled with numerical approximation of the curing kinetics for thermosetting polymer resins. Major pultrusion mechanisms (heat transfer and degree-of-curing) can be simulated for two-dimensional pultruded polymer matrix composites. The pultrusion processes of AS4/EPON-9420/9470/537 CF/epoxy composite rods were simulated and the results were compared to those in the literature. The approach developed in this study can be easily adopted to tailor two-dimensional pultrusion processes in practical applications.

KEYWORDS: pultrusion, heat transfer, degree-of-cure, finite element model

INTRODUCTION

Pultrusion is one of the most cost-effective techniques for manufacturing composite structural components with a constant cross-section, being applicable for both thermoset and thermoplastic matrix composites. A typical pultrusion system, Figure 1, consists of creels for feeding dry reinforcing fibres, a resin bath for impregnation, a heated forming die for consolidation and curing, pulling mechanisms for pulling the product at constant speed, and a cut-off saw to cut the part to the desired length.

In most practical approaches to pultrusion, a variety of means have been applied to impregnate reinforcing materials with resins. Almost all types of filamentary reinforcing materials can be used, such as rovings, tows, mats, cloth or any hybrid of these. The most widely used reinforcing material is fibreglass, e.g. E glass and S glass fibres. Pultrusion-grade resin matrices are available in a variety of systems such as polyester, epoxy, vinyl ester and phenolic resins. Unsaturated polyester resins are most commonly used because of low heat input required with faster gelation compared to other resin systems.

To produce pultruded products with consistent and high quality, it is important to tailor and control the pultrusion process. To achieve a uniform degree-of-cure in the cross section of a product, the temperature profile inside of the pultrusion die is an essential aspect. Therefore, it is important to develop mechanics models to simulate the pultrusion process, and in turn to tailor the process.

As the resin-impregnated fibre tows enter the die, the heat is transferred from the die wall to the compacted fibre-resin blend. Due to the low thermal conductivity of the blend, the temperature at the centre of the material is lower than that near the die wall. However, when the temperature in the blend reaches a critical level at which the catalyst becomes activated, the curing reaction begins and generates heat due to the exothermic reaction, which causes the temperature at the centre to be higher than that near the wall. Therefore, the temperature profile in the composite material inside the forming die is a balance of heat transfer and exothermic reaction.

Figure 1. The diagram of the pultrusion process

Several models have been developed to gain a fundamental understanding of pultrusion process. Using a finite difference method, Han and Lee [1] applied an empirical kinetic model with a prescribed wall temperature profile in the simulation. Pultrusion characteristics were studied with variables such as resin type, fibre type, catalyst type, and the pulling speed. It was concluded that kinetic parameters need to be determined individually for each material system and each pultruded cross-section profile. Batch and Macosko [2] developed a pultrusion model based on a kinetic approach that includes a heat transfer model, a resin pressure model, and a pulling force model. The resin pressure was described assuming that the fibre-resin blend acts like an anisotropic porous media. Darcy's law was used for the fluid continuity to express the dependency of fluid pressure on the resin density, viscosity, and the volume fraction of fibres. Hackett and Prasad [3] applied a one-dimensional finite element model based on the Galerkin weighted residual method to solve the heat transfer equations, with liquid and solid sub-models to define the gelation point. This approach was later extended to predict temperature distributions and the degree-of-cure inside pultruded composites along the pultrusion line [4], and a convective boundary condition was assumed to replace the prescribed wall temperature profiles. An unsteady state model was developed by Wu and Joseph [5] to describe transient conditions for start-up or change of operation conditions, which includes the degree-of-cure, and temperature distributions in the material and die. Ma and Chen [6] developed a kinetic model for heat transfer to predict profiles of temperature and degree-of-cure in a pultruded glass fibre composite of a rectangular cross section for a block polyurethane resin using a finite difference method. It was found that the proposed kinetic model described well the curing behaviour of reinforced block polyurethane resins using appropriate kinetic parameters. Batch and Macosko [7] developed a more comprehensive model to describe the effects of radio frequency (RF) preheating, changes of thermal properties with temperature and degree-of-cure, hindered cooling due to shrinkage of the profile away from the die wall, air cooling of the profile while outside the die. The equations of transient heat transfer and reaction kinetics were solved by implicit finite difference methods. Gorthala et al [8] focused on the development of models for describing effects of velocity profiles including slip velocity as well as gelation length. Degree-of-cure, and viscosity of the resin at gelation were simulated.

In the previous studies simulations were mainly conducted using a self-developed finite difference or finite element program coupled with the curing kinetics. The main objective of this study is to develop a new procedure to simulate the pultrusion process using a commercial finite element software and numerical approximation of curing kinetics. The major principles can be applied to any other commercial finite element packages, which in turn makes the simulation of pultrusion process much more cost-effective.

Figure 2: Pultrusion model in cartesian coordinates

PROCESS MODELING

From previous analyses, the basic assumptions of the present pultrusion model are:

- 1) the process is two-dimensional at a steady state;
- 2) the matrix and fibre have the same temperature at any point, i.e. the material is homogeneous; and
- 3) the influence of pressure on the heat of reaction is neglected.

Based on those assumptions, the equation of heat transfer can be expressed as [4],

$$\rho c u \frac{\partial T}{\partial x} - \frac{\partial}{\partial x} (k_x \frac{\partial T}{\partial x}) - \frac{\partial}{\partial y} (k_y \frac{\partial T}{\partial y}) - H_r \rho m_m \frac{\partial \alpha}{\partial t} = 0 \quad (1)$$

where

- T = temperature of the material
- k = thermal conductivity of the material
- c = heat capacity of the material
- u = pultrusion line speed
- H_r = ultimate heat of reaction
- m_m = mass fraction of matrix
- α = degree-of-cure
- ρ = density of the material

This global heat transfer model can be further divided into two basic sub-models: i.e. heat transfer defined by the first three terms and curing process by the last term. In this study, the solution of Equation 1 is approached using an iterative technique of two sub-models.

Heat Transfer

Since the top and bottom heat platens of the die are assumed to be at the same temperature, the process is symmetric about its mid-plane. Therefore, the process is only simulated for the bottom half shown in Figure 2. The boundary conditions can be expressed as,

$$T(0,y) = T_0 \quad (2a)$$

$$T(x,0) = T_D(x) \quad (2b)$$

where T_0 is the material temperature at the entrance of the die, and T_D the die wall temperature.

As a first order approach, it is assumed that for the composite within the die, thermal properties are independent of the curing state of the composite. In this case, the thermal properties of the composite can be approximated using micromechanics analysis of fibre reinforced composite

$$\rho = \rho_m v_m + \rho_f (1 - v_m) \quad (3)$$

$$c = m_m c_m + (1 - m_m) c_f \quad (4)$$

$$k_{x,y} = \frac{1}{\frac{m_m}{k_m} + \frac{(1 - m_m)}{k_{f,x,y}}} \quad (5)$$

materials from the constituent properties [9], where the subscripts m and f refer to matrix and fibre, respectively, $k_{x,y}$ the thermal conductivity in the x and y directions, c the heat capacity, v_m the matrix volume fraction, and m_m the matrix mass fraction.

Curing Model

The curing within the pultruded composite is a complex chemical reaction process that has not been clearly understood [4]. Relationships among temperature, degree-of-cure, and rate-of-cure have been established for several commercial pultruded grade resins [4,10]. Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) was normally applied to measure the heat reaction and the rate-of-cure. The relationship between the rate-of-cure ($d\alpha/dt$) and the degree-of-cure (α) can be approximated using a modified Arrhenius type equation [10],

$$\frac{d\alpha}{dt} = K_o \exp\left(\frac{-\Delta E_A}{RT}\right) (1 - \alpha)^n \quad (6)$$

where K_o is a pre-exponential constant, ΔE_A the activation energy, R the universal gas constant, and n the order of reaction.

Numerical Simulation

From the governing differential equation (Eq. 1), it can be seen that the temperature state and the degree-of-cure are coupled, and they have to be solved simultaneously. In this case, an iteration technique is applied. Firstly, it is assumed that the degree-of-cure is zero everywhere in the composite. Then the finite element analysis is performed to obtain the initial state of the

temperature for each element. Using the temperature profile, the rate-of-cure for each element is calculated using Eq. 6. At the entrance of the die, the resin enters the die in the form of an uncured liquid such that starting from this entrance line, the degree-of-cure is equal to zero at any step of iteration, i.e.

$$\alpha(0,y) = 0 \quad (7)$$

As it was mentioned in the previous section that the process is assumed to be at a steady state, and the flow of composite is assumed to be only along the x axis of the die (the velocity in the y direction is neglected), such that time is only a function of x [4]. Therefore, the rate-of-cure can be defined by the derivation with respect to x rather than to time.

$$\frac{\partial \alpha}{\partial x} = \frac{l}{u} \frac{\partial \alpha}{\partial t} \quad (8)$$

Once the rate-of-cure with respect to x for each element is obtained, the next step is to integrate the gradient to find the degree-of-cure (α) [4].

$$\alpha(x + \Delta x, y) = \alpha(x, y) + \frac{l}{2} \left[\frac{\partial \alpha}{\partial x}(x, y) + \frac{\partial \alpha}{\partial x}(x + \Delta x, y) \right] \Delta x \quad (9)$$

where Δx is the distance between the centers of the adjacent elements.

This degree-of-cure profile will be applied to calculate the temperature profile for a new step of iteration using the finite element analysis. In general, the iteration procedure may be simply summarised as a flowchart shown in Figure 3. The criterion for convergence is set such that the difference in temperatures at each node obtained between two consecutive iterations is not greater than 1°C.

EVALUATIONS AND DISCUSSION

Simulations were performed for pultruded composite rods with a diameter of 0.95 cm, using the data obtained by Valliappan et al [10] for a AS4/EPON 9420/9470/537 graphite/epoxy system. This reference was chosen since it provides experimental and numerical results for verification. The die length was 91.4 cm with three different pulling speeds of 20, 30 and 40 cm/min, respectively. The thermal properties of the system and kinetic parameters for the epoxy are given Tables 1 and 2, respectively. The typical profile of die wall temperature and the simulation of centerline temperature distribution are presented in Figure 4. In the region near the entrance of the die, the die wall temperature is higher than that of the centerline, with the die releasing heat to the composite during the curing reaction. The length of this zone depends on the pulling speed; the higher the pulling speed is, the longer this zone [4]. The temperature of the composite

beyond that zone is higher than that of the die wall due to accumulation of heat generated by the exothermal curing process. In evaluations, the solution of the heat transfer sub-model was obtained using an ABAQUS FEM package, and the curing sub-model was approximated using numerical solutions, based on the procedure in Figure 3.

Table 1. Thermal Properties of AS4/EPON 9420/9470/537 Composite Material [10]

Material	Density (g/cm ³)	Specific Heat (J/g.K)	Thermal Conductivity (W/m.K)
Fibre	1.790	0.712	k _{fy} = 11.6 k _{fx} = 66.0
Matrix	1.260	1.255	0.2

Table 2. Kinetic Parameters of Shell EPON 9420/9470/537 epoxy resin [10]

Parameters	Symbol	Value
Pre-exponential constant	K_0	19.14 x 10 ⁴ [s ⁻¹]
Activation energy	E_A	60.5 x 10 ³ [J/mol]
Heat reaction	ΔH	323.7 [J/g]
Order of reaction	n	1.69

Effect of Mesh Discretization

Since the heat is transported from the die to the composite by two mechanisms (convection and conduction), the relative amount of heat transferred is expressed by the Peclet Number (Pe) [11] defined by,

$$Pe = \frac{\rho c u L}{k} \quad (10)$$

where L is the length of the element along the direction of the flow. Because the nature of finite element method is the central difference [11], it yields a reasonable solution only when the value of Pe is low (should be less than 2 theoretically) [12]. However, when Pe is too large (convection dominates the system), false oscillations are generated, which may conceal the true solution[11].

Figure 3. Iteration procedure to solve temperature and degree-of-cure.

Figure 4. A typical centerline temperature profile of the pultrusion process.

In this study, the small Peclet Number was obtained by refining the element size in the direction of the flow. Three different meshes were created uniformly using four-node elements, producing Peclet Number of 96, 12 and 3 at a pulling speed of $u = 30$ cm/minute. The element number for each mesh along the centerline was 99, 792, and 3168, respectively (with two rows of the element along the y axis for every mesh) and the boundary conditions of Eqs 2a and 2b were applied to each mesh. Figure 5 shows the effect of Peclet Number on temperature profiles at the centerline. For Peclet Number = 96, the result shows a sharp increase in the middle of the die length to a value of above 600 °K. This divergence is caused by the coarse mesh being used. The results for Peclet Number = 12 or 3 show a good agreement with that obtained by Valliappan et al [10] (prediction and experimentation). Figure 6 presents the effect of Peclet Number on degree-of-cure. Since the degree-of-cure is dependent on temperature, the results are correlated to the temperature distributions. For Peclet Number = 96 the curing process is already complete at the middle of the die, which is not realistic. For the cases of $Pe=12$ and $Pe=3$ the results are in agreement with those obtained by Valliappan et al [10].

Effect of Initial Boundary Condition

Before entering the die, the temperature of the material (fibre and resin) was assumed to be close to the ambient temperature (300 °K). This assumption was then applied to the finite element model for heat transfer with Peclet Number of 96 at a pulling speed of 30 cm/min. The results are presented in Figures 7 and 8 together with those obtained from the finite element model for Peclet Number = 3 but without the initial condition. It can be seen that both results show the same temperature distribution along the die length.

Figure 5. Effect of Peclet Number on centerline temperature profiles at pulling speed of 30 cm/min.

Figure 6. Effect of Peclet Number on centerline degree-of-cure at pulling speed of 30 cm/min.

This phenomenon is caused by the iterative starting point of the FEM analysis. If the initial condition for temperature is not specified, the finite element program assumes that the initial condition is 0 °K. It was found that the initial boundary condition does not have a visible influence on the results if Peclet Number is small. Furthermore, it can be seen that coarser mesh can still achieve accurate results by adding the initial boundary condition to the model. However, some commercial FEM packages do not provide the initial boundary condition which means that application of the fine meshes to avoid inaccuracy of the results becomes necessary.

Figure 7. Centerline temperature profiles obtained with and without initial boundary conditions.

Figure 8. Centerline degree-of-cure profiles obtained with and without initial boundary conditions.

Effect of Pulling Speed

Three different pulling speeds were applied in the simulations with $Pe = 96$ and the initial boundary condition. Figure 9 shows centerline temperature distributions with different pulling speeds but with the same die wall temperature. It can be seen that when the pulling speed is increased, the initial lag of the centerline temperature increases. This is caused by the fact that as the pulling speed is raised, the time available for heat transfer to the center of the composite becomes shorter, which causes the centerline temperature of the composite to be less than that at a low pulling speed. On the degree-of-cure profiles, it can be seen that when the pulling speed is increased, the degree-of-cure at the die exit decreases. To obtain a sufficiently cured product at a high pulling speed, either the die wall temperature or the die length has to be increased.

Figure 9. Effect of pulling speed on centerline temperature profiles ($Pe = 96$ with initial boundary condition).

Figure 10. Effect of pulling speed on centerline degree-of-cure profiles ($Pe = 96$ with initial boundary condition).

CONCLUSION

Combining the finite element model (FEM) for heat transfer and the numerical approximation for curing kinetics, profiles of centerline temperature and degree-of-cure were simulated for a pultruded carbon/epoxy composite. Effects of finite element mesh, initial temperature condition for FEM analysis and pulling speed on the pultrusion process were studied. Comparisons of the results to those published by Valliappan et al [10] show good agreements. Based on the methodology used in this study, a procedure to simulate profiles of temperature and degree-of-cure of pultruded composites can be easily adopted using a commercial finite element software.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

B. R. Suratno is grateful for the award of a postgraduate scholarship tenable at the University of Sydney by the Australian Agency for International Development (AusAID). L. Ye and Y. W. Mai would like to acknowledge the continuing support of this project by the Australian Research Council (ARC).

REFERENCES

1. Han, C. D. and D. S. Lee. "Development of a Mathematical Model for the Pultrusion Process," *Polymer Engineering and Science*, Vol. 26, 1986, pp. 393-404.
2. Batch, G. L. and C. W. Macosko. "Heat Transfer and Cure in Pultrusion: Model and Experimental Verification," *AIChE Journal*, Vol. 39, 1993, pp. 1228-1241.
3. Hacket, R. M. and S. N. Prasad. "Pultrusion Process Modeling," *Advances in Thermoplastic Matrix composite Materials*, G. M. Newaz, ed., ASTM STP 1044, American Society for Testing and Materials, 1989, pp. 62-70.
4. Hacket, R. M. and S. Zhu. "Two-Dimensional Finite Element Model of the Pultrusion Process," *Journal of Reinforced Plastics and Composites*, Vol. 2, 1992, pp. 1322-1351.
5. Wu, H. and B. Joseph. "Model Based and Knowledge Based Control of Pultrusion Processes," *SAMPE Journal*, Vol. 26, 1990, pp. 59-70.
6. Ma, E. M. and C. Chen. "The Development of a Mathematical Model for the Pultrusion of Blocked Polyurethane Composites," *Journal of Applied Polymer Science*, Vol. 50, 1993, pp. 759-764.
7. Batch, G. L. and C. W. Macosko. "A Computer Analysis of Temperature and Pressure Distribution in a Pultrusion Die," *42nd Annual Conference*, The Society of Plastics Industry, Inc., 1987, pp. 1-7.
8. Gorthala, R., J. A. Roux and J. G. Vaughan. "Resin Flow, Cure and Heat Transfer Analysis for Pultrusion Process," *Journal of Composite Materials*, Vol. 28, 1994, pp. 486-506.
9. Jones, R. M., *Mechanics of Composites Materials*, McGraw-Hill, New York, 1980.
10. Valliappan, M., Roux, J. A., Vaughan, J. G., and Arafat, E. S. "Die and Post-die Temperature and Cure in Graphite/Epoxy Composites," *Composites: Part B*, Vol. 27B, 1996, pp. 1-9.
11. Huang, H. C. and Usmani, A. S., *Finite Element Analysis for Heat Transfer*, Springer-Verlag, London, 1994.
12. Patankar, S. V., *Numerical Heat Transfer and Fluid Flow*, McGraw-Hill, New York, 1980.